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Customer Relationship Management in Ghanaian Rural Banks: A Case Study of Upper Manya Kro Rural Bank

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Description CRM has become widely recognized as an important business approach and it is basically about finding, getting and retaining customers. The primary goals of CRM are to: build long-term and profitable relationships with chosen customers; get closer to those customers at every point of contact; and maximize the company's share of the customer's wallet. On this note the study therefore set out to investigate the dynamics of customer relationship management in Upper Manya Kro Rural Bank Limited in Ghana. In pursuit of this goal, the study reviewed relevant secondary data gathered from the internet, journals and publications on the subject of the research. Primary data was collected from ten (10) customer relationship officers purposively selected from 6 branches of Upper Manya Kro Rural Bank. The responses gathered from the interviews were analysed, interpreted and presented qualitatively and contrasted with ...

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